

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BHALEKAR****FIRST NAME: ASHVIN****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied **UK** conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author **did** use Zotero to insert references

The author **did** use Grammarly Premium

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (MSWord)

List of Seven (7) key concepts with page number in text:

1. Understanding the essence and guidelines of essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 6-10)
2. Essay writing requires timely action (EUCLID 2021, 7-13)
3. Research must be backed up by trustworthy sources (EUCLID 2021, 8-9)
4. Combination of critical and creative thinking (EUCLID 2021, 9)
5. Write clearly and simply (EUCLID 2021, 13)
6. Technical and grammatical aspects are very important (EUCLID 2021, 15)
7. Plagiarism impairs credibility and value (EUCLID 2021, 33)

RETHINKING ACADEMIC WRITING: A JOURNEY OF CLARITY, PRECISION, AND DISCIPLINE

1) INTRODUCTION

For me, starting my doctorate studies in this course has been a very humbling experience. I joined the course with some confidence, thinking that my past knowledge and expertise would make this journey reasonably easy, having practiced law for 27 years in various Indian courts and earning two master's degrees in the field. But with all due humility, I have to say that this course has been a great eye-opener. I have learned that the art of academic writing is a continuous process. It is demanding and requires careful attention to structure, clarity, and understanding.

Even though I have practical legal knowledge from my work experience, this course has opened my eyes to new aspects of academic involvement and discipline. I have realized that there is scope for great improvement, learning, and growth in pursuit of this doctorate study. The ACA-401D course pack has given me a better understanding of the art and science of academic writing. Writing is not merely putting ideas on paper; it's a method

and a process that requires focus, creativity, and clarity. I found the following seven fundamental ideas, among others, to be extremely relevant in this course.

2) UNDERSTANDING THE ESSENCE AND GUIDELINES OF ESSAY WRITING

According to the key Approaches listed there, this course material was nothing less than a "catalyst for transformation." When I started this course, I was heavily burdened by my prior experiences and beliefs. Thanks to the training, I was able to remove my previous notions about academic writing and reestablish a method based on accuracy, discipline, and analysis.

The foundation is a proper and significant comprehension of the rules and structure of academic writing. An essay is more than just a list of words; it is a coherent work of writing that explains ideas understandably and rationally. Every essay I have found needs a beginning, middle, and end: a brief introduction, paragraphs that bolster the argument and provide evidence, and a clear conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 6-10). By following these rules, the essay becomes an effective and coherent research work.

3) ESSAY WRITING REQUIRES TIMELY ACTION

Writing for academic purposes requires discipline and is governed by consistent, deliberate, and focused work. It suffers greatly from procrastination. One of the most important lessons I have learned is the importance of quick action, which includes starting early, planning well, and maintaining a steady pace. The first stage is to establish the "essay question," which entails dissecting it correctly, looking at the key elements that need to be elaborated, and identifying the theme in detail (EUCLID 2021, 7-13). Maintaining focus on the topic prevents unnecessary digressions, and setting reasonable deadlines ensures that the essay is not rushed but rather enhanced gradually. This approach has taught me that writing essays is a journey rather than a race.

4) RESEARCH MUST BE BACKED UP BY TRUSTWORTHY SOURCES

Good research is essential to an effective essay. A well-written essay is built on a foundation of trustworthy and properly referenced research. In the current digital age, where research and references are available on the net at your fingertips, it is extremely challenging to understand the authenticity of the sources. It is pertinent that the research is carried out with utmost sincerity and hard work, without relying upon superficial and unreliable sources (EUCLID 2021, 8-9). Correct research will enhance the quality of the essay; an insincere and haphazard survey will damage the essay. I realized that active reading and note-making is an essential ingredient of good research. Additionally,

allocating proper and dedicated time to research is the key. Research is a time-consuming process and will have to be carried out methodically. There are no shortcuts in research; it is a lengthy process that is to be conducted in a wholesome manner.

5) COMBINATION OF CRITICAL AND CREATIVE THINKING

Appropriately expressing your thoughts and ideas in the form of words is only one aspect of writing an effective essay; an equally important aspect is to do so critically and creatively (EUCLID 2021, 9). Critical thinking is the ability to analytically scrutinize and express your views. Similarly, creative thinking is the ability to develop your propositions in a unique manner. I will have to consciously ensure that every argument in an essay is supported by research and evidence, avoiding flimsy or unsubstantiated assertions; and at the same time, it is creatively enriching.

6) WRITE CLEARLY AND SIMPLY

Flowery and fanciful language does not serve any purpose in academic writing. Effective academic writing is characterized by simplicity. The temptation to use heavily decorative language ought to be resisted. I have to bear this particular lesson in my mind. Being a practicing lawyer for 27 years has made me prone to use heavy language. I have to focus on simplicity and clarity and refrain from using terms that are not absolutely necessary. A simple, meaningful phrase in an essay is more effective in conveying the writer's thoughts (EUCLID 2021, 13).

7) TECHNICAL AND GRAMMATICAL ASPECTS ARE VERY IMPORTANT

I must admit one fact here. I always thought that punctuation was nothing more than an insignificant grammatical matter. It represents unimportant features that can be easily overlooked. After carefully reading the course materials, I realized the significance of punctuation. It is an essential ingredient of effective communication and academic writing (EUCLID 2021, 15). It is an important aspect of professional academic writing. I have learned from the course that punctuation marks give a proper structure and clarity to the essay. Every punctuation mark, such as apostrophes, colons, semicolons etc, has a definite function.

8) PLAGIARISM IMPAIRS CREDIBILITY AND VALUE

Plagiarism is a clear violation of academic integrity. The course pack has shown me how crucial it is to acknowledge the original author's thoughts, arguments, and research. To create your own essay, you must build on other people's ideas while acknowledging

their contributions. Proper citation through in-text references and a comprehensive bibliography help avoid plagiarism and enhance the essay's worth (EUCLID 2021, 33). Using resources like the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) for citations ensures expertise and consistency.

9) CONCLUSION

It has been a long and delayed effort on my part to complete this paper. I have been able to do so only due to the help offered by the ACA-401D course pack. This course has completely changed my perspective on academic writing. I was initially hesitant and self-conscious when I started writing my answer paper. I was not sure if I could handle the demanding requirements of doctorate study. But reading the course pack gave me a road map, and I walked along. I intend to continue and pursue further steps to the best of my abilities. I see it as an opportunity for personal enrichment and development.

REFERENCES

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